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SOME PROBLEMS AND USEFUL APPROACHES FOR RUSSIAN TRANSLATION OF GASTRONOMIC TEXTS

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The article describes some common problems that are encountered by the translators of the gastronomic texts. These texts constitute an important part of any country's culture, convey its image across the world and promote its international recognition. Gastronomic texts can be very different because they are used as encyclopedic entries, magazine articles, menu items and in many other areas. In today's globalized world, cuisine becomes increasingly important for any country's economy. Therefore, gastronomic texts are an important area of translation. Their translation styles are dictated by the kind of the gastronomic texts and the work aims.

The article contains a brief analysis of the most frequent lexical, grammatical and stylistic aspects of peculiarities of the gastronomic text translation. It points out that, apart from the linguistic aspects, the translator should take into account cultural realia, history, traditions of the country to render its peculiar cuisine. Thus, extra-curricular knowledge is essential for the translation of gastronomic texts. Dictionaries, special literature and the Internet sites on gastronomy are used for writing this material.

Key words: *cuisine, gastronomy, recipe, translation, difficulty, culture, approach, cooking*

CÂTEVA PROBLEME ȘI ABORDĂRI UTILE PENTRU TRADUCEREA ÎN LIMBA RUSĂ A TEXTELOR GASTRONOMICE

Articolul descrie câteva dificultăți cu care se confruntă traducătorii textelor gastronomice. Aceste texte constituie o parte importantă a culturii oricărei țări, transmit imaginea în întreaga lume și promovează recunoașterea internațională. Textele gastronomice pot fi foarte diferite deoarece sunt folosite ca intrări enciclopedice, articole de reviste, de meniu. În lumea globalizată de astăzi, bucătăria devine din ce în ce mai importantă pentru economia oricărei țări. Prin urmare, textele gastronomice reprezintă un domeniu important de traducere. Stilurile lor de traducere sunt dictate de tipul textelor gastronomice și de scopul acestor texte.

Articolul conține o scurtă analiză a celor mai frecvente aspecte lexicale, gramaticale și stilistice ale particularităților traducerii textului gastronomic. În afară de

aspectele lingvistice, traducătorul trebuie să țină cont de realitățile culturale, istoria, tradițiile țării. Astfel, cunoștințele extracurriculare sunt esențiale pentru traducerea textelor gastronomice.

Cuvinte-cheie: *bucătărie, gastronomie, rețetă, traducere, dificultate, cultură, abordare, gătit*

The translation of the gastronomic texts is one of the most challenging tasks even for the experienced professionals. In today's globalized world, gastronomic translations have become a crucial question of both cultural and commercial nature, because they help promote the country's international image and recognition. The interest towards unusual, healthy and tasty food is growing all over the world and the rich cuisine of the Republic of Moldova has a lot to offer. Gastronomic texts can tell a lot not only about the cuisine of the country, but also about its culture, people and traditions. In this article, there is an attempt to look into some difficulties related to the translation of gastronomic texts and to offer some useful strategies for handling them.

On the one side, cuisines of various cultures are very different from the one of the target language and include a lot of unknown ingredients. The translator should be ready to encounter a lot of language-specific cultural realia, for which they cannot find equivalents in their languages. As it is mentioned in the textbook 'Introduction into Translation Studies', "Frequently, there is no lexical equivalent in the target language. Cultural realia are frequently loaned in this form – the target language element may seem better, more precise, better sounding, more fashionable". [1, p. 73] So, borrowing of the gastronomic terms seems to be one of the easiest solutions, but in many cases it is impossible because the translation will not be understandable. An excess of borrowed words will make the translation intelligible for professionals only and the general public will not be able to access it.

Speaking of gastronomy and its linguistic peculiarities, it is important to mention that this problem has a few dimensions, such as names of dishes, their ingredients as well as the verbs and tools related to their cooking and consumption. In spite of the fact that a lot of them have long become internationalisms like pizza, pasta, sushi or hamburgers, from time to time, translators come across new names of meals, because they are less known or are of relatively recent coinage. For example, a lot of meals of the Moldovan cuisine, such as 'sarmale' or 'mitetei' can hardly be known to English speakers but they

are essential for any book on Moldovan cuisine. [2, p. 43] Hence, the translators should develop some strategies that could be used to make the recipes accessible to the foreign public.

According to the Scopos theory, any translation is done with a purpose. Depending on the aim of the translations, they can never be judged just in terms of ‘equivalence’ and ‘faithfulness’, because the purpose role is also essential. [3, p. 2190] It is also important what kind of gastronomic text is dealt with – a cookery-book, a single recipe, instructions for cooking or a literary description to name a few. If the translation is addressed to home cooking, the language is simplified and has a lot of descriptions, but if it is intended for scientific, encyclopedic or other special literature, there will be more specific terminology.

On the other side, there are a lot of similarities between the cuisines of different countries that could help the translation but it is often impossible to render the original terminology into the target language. For example, when translating the meals of the Moldovan cuisine, it is not possible to translate ‘mămăligă’ as ‘polenta’, because the former is a distant analogue in Italian cuisine as mămăligă requires some special procedures when cooking and is served with a lot of garnishes not typical of polenta and its eating even includes some cultural ceremonies like cutting it with a thread. The more general term ‘maize porridge’ is not suitable either as the traditional meal would be deprived of its cultural and regional peculiarity and would seem to be primitive. [4] In this case, translators are supposed to keep the original denomination of the meal, but they encounter another problem – how to clarify this denomination to the readers who do not know the meal in question? The reader of the target text will have a vague idea what kind of meal is described in the text, if they are not given some clarifications. The traditional references are not always available, because of a specific type of the printed matter. Therefore, the translator should also take into account the type of the product where this translation will appear. Depending on its being a leaflet, a cookery-book or a newspaper article, the clarification of the unknown meal title can be brackets, footnotes or it can even constitute a picture in a restaurant menu. Moreover, for the commercial purposes, the menu items can be named even more unconventionally than household meals and that also prevents from their rendering in another language. Besides, the menu genre actually provokes to order the meal and this should be pertained in the translation.

It is interesting to mention the difference between the gastronomic units even within the English language from different countries. For example, English ‘high tea’ that is something in between a tea party and dinner with the family and friends shows towards the social approach to this meal. [5] At the same time, American gastronomic discourse is often related to enjoyment, received from the meal, even at the expense of its being harmful. Such terms as ‘junk food’ and ‘fast food’ were coined within the American English language. [ibid.]

The ingredients themselves can constitute a considerable problem as not all kinds of dough, cheese, wines, vegetables and fruit used for different national recipes should be normally translated. However, the readers are not likely to know them all. Furthermore, even when the translator sees a word that seems obvious for the translation, it may happen to be a false friend in some cases and “turn out to have very different meanings from those believed on the basis of the similarity with the mother tongue, being deceptive and tricky”. [1, p.71] For instance, the English term ‘delicatessen’ can be translated not only as ‘luxury foods’, but also as ‘food shop’, ‘gastronomy’ and even ‘salads’. [6] The translator has to possess profound extra-linguistic knowledge in order to render the names of the meals correctly. Another interesting point to be borne in mind is polysemy, because a lot of gastronomic terms have various interpretations. The word ‘pudding’ is another good example, because it can be translated in a number of ways meaning any sweet meal or even some food of the same texture. [7]

There are even more subtle nuances. Translators often stumble with difference between the words ‘broth’ and ‘stock’. Broth is rather a separate dish or a by-product of the boiled meats or vegetables after boiling and it can be consumed in itself, albeit there is a terminological confusion even with the professionals. When this soup after boiling meat or vegetables is just a component for a more complex meal, the right word is stock. [6]

Another problem is the difference between British English, American English and local dialects of other English-speaking countries and localities. For instance, the Russian words “баклажан” in British English is aubergine, but it is eggplant in American English. The Romanian word “dovliceu” is courgettes in British English and zucchini in American English. [7]

Another point that can present possible difficulty is the translation of cutlery, crockery and other useful tools necessary for cooking the meals in question. Chopsticks are internationally recognized with the lovers of Chinese

and Japanese cuisines, but other terms used for the food cooking and consumption may not be so recognizable. Also, the translator should also bear in mind different measurements that are used in the recipes. Such terms as ‘spoonful’, ‘cupful’, ‘handful’, ‘plateful’ and others refer to the imperial system of measurements, together with pounds and ounces. [8] The decision between the metric system of measurements and the imperial system in English recipes can also constitute a problem. English has become one of the international languages and English translations can be addressed to readers all over the world. Those living in the United Kingdom, the USA and English-speaking countries are used to measuring the meals with the imperial system, but if gastronomic English translations are intended for other countries, kilograms and grams are also highly advisable. In fact, it is not difficult to duplicate the information about the measurements in brackets when the translation is addressed to wide readership. The necessary adaptations are strongly advisable to escape possible misunderstanding of the amounts of the ingredients but they may harm aesthetic perception of the text and confuse the readers.

There are fewer grammar difficulties of English gastronomic translations, as the grammar of the gastronomic texts is rather laconic and is usually confined by the Imperative Mood and impersonal constructions. However, there are some specific aspects to be borne in mind. First, the register and style of the translation are important. The translator should use the style and register of the original or make a translation typical of the target language. For example, the translator has to decide if the sentences are rendered in full, or they will include instructions written as elliptic sentences, where some parts of the sentences will be eliminated. As Michael Swan mentions, the instructions often ignore the articles. For instance, “Take 500g butter and place in small saucepan”. [9, p.182] Here we see the article omission before ‘sauce pan’. So, the cookery-books are written in both styles: they can contain elliptic instructions or look like more literary texts depending on the strategy chosen by the translator or the intention of the text. At the same time, when being translated into another language, they may change their style according to the norms of the target text. For example, Russian recipes also include the Imperative mood with the infinitive constructions (“добавить”, "нарезать") or the second-person perfect verbs (“выкладываете”, "снимаете") [10, p.44].

Rendering gastronomic terminology into the languages with Cyrillic alphabets, like Russian, translators often use transliteration and transcription, for example, ‘macaroni’ is rendered as “макароны” or partial transcription – ‘fondue de tomates’ may be translated as “фондю из томатов”. Calque is another usual approach, for instance, “spicy pancake” may be rendered as “пикантный блинчик”.

Speaking of other strategies used for the gastronomic translation, first of all, it is necessary to mention the most applicable for different kinds of translation – restructuring, modulation, addition, omission and transposition. For instance, in the English recipes, when using the Imperative Mood, verbs are usually used first and the name of the product follows it. In Russian recipes, just the opposite, the product is often mentioned before the verb. Addition, omission and modulation are used to solve the translation problems in order to make the translation more natural and looking like original text [1, p. 60].

The translator who has taken everything above-mentioned into account may still commit a lot of mistakes dealing with gastronomic texts. It is related to the fact that a cuisine of another country is closely related to its linguistic and cultural components, way of life and history of the country. The translator should investigate the civilization of the country in order to understand a lot of information that is not obvious. The modern restaurant sophisticated language makes this problem even more difficult, because the restaurant chefs try to attract their clients to the cuisine and this attempt should also be considered in the translation. One cannot make a good translation without deep understanding of the subject and profound extra-curricular knowledge of the topic.

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